

Large Language Models to generate sonic behaviors: the case of *Wilding AI* in exploring creative co- agency

Alexandre Saunier

LUCA School of Arts, KU Leuven
Zurich University of the Arts (ZHdK)
saunier.alexandre@yahoo.com

Federico Visi

Luleå University of Technology
federico.visi@gmail.com

Maurice Jones

Concordia University
maurice@mutek.jp

Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) and foundational models play a central role in multimodal text-to-sound systems, such as text-to-speech and text-to-music, as well as in recent musical agent systems designed to automate music production tasks. We explore an alternative approach that employs LLM-based sonic agents as spatial composition techniques. This method, emerging from the *Wilding AI* research-creation project, integrates LLMs into Max/MSP, Ableton Live, and spatial sound environments. LLMs are used to generate step-by-step sequences controlling spatial audio parameters, including sound motion in 3D space and other assignable sound properties. This paper details the artistic framework of *Wilding AI*, a LLM behavior generator, a live performance at the CTM Festival 2025, and discussions on composition, improvisation, time, and agency. Our work repositions LLMs as tools for shaping sonic experiences rather than merely generating finished audio material.

1 Introduction

This paper presents an experimental artistic application of Large Language Models (LLMs) as a spatial composition technique for producing sonic motion. Departing from mainstream uses such as text-to-music and text-to-voice content generation, we introduce an LLM-based behavior generator that enables artists to produce dynamic sound motion and parameter modulation through textual prompts.

Emerging from the research-creation project *Wilding AI*—a collaboration among sound and media artists and researchers committed to resisting techno-solutionist uses of generative AI—this approach seeks to open space for artistic and cultural diversity in creative AI practices. We combine aspects of research-creation, behavior perception, creative coding, and musical composition and performance to discuss an original use of LLMs as behavior generators producing dynamic spatial motion.

In section 2, we provide a brief overview of *Wilding AI*'s research-creation framework. In section 3, we outline the conceptual basis of the LLM behavior generator, grounded in research on the perception of apparent behavior, artificial intelligence, and robotics. In section 4, we detail the technical implementation of the behavior generator developed in Max/MSP. In section 5, we present an account of an experimental performance conducted during an open

call workshop held at CTM Festival in Berlin in January 2025. In section 6, we reflect on the project team's and workshop participants' experiences, and share insights into the application of LLMs in processes of sonic creation. Finally, in the conclusion, we argue for the importance of critically examining the emerging creative uses of LLMs—and foundational models more broadly—in relation to the long-standing traditions of musical practices that employ aleatoric, stochastic, and other generative strategies.

2 *Wilding AI's* Research-Creation Context

Wilding AI is an ongoing research-creation project aiming to resist attempts at the narrative closure and technical stabilization of generative AI toward standardized technologies aiming to replace human creativity with automated. Initiated in the Spring of 2024, the project involves a multidisciplinary collective of sound and media artists, technologists, and academics mainly based in Canada and Europe. As of Spring 2025, the core collective involves Alexandre Saunier, Beth Coleman, Daniela Huerta, Debashis Sinha, Gadi Sassoon, Heu Hsu, Maurice Jones, Nao Tokui, Pia Baltazar, Portrait XO, and Sahar Homani.

Conceptually, *Wilding AI* follows Beth Coleman's invitation to conceive AI systems “that can be free—if not to imagine then to generate—speeding through possibilities, junctures that are idiotic until they are not” (Coleman 2021). Grounded in her reading of AI technologies through the historical practice of marronage—runaway slaves that established autonomous spaces and communities in North America and the Caribbean—, Coleman's notion of “wilding” seeks to develop new conceptual approaches that resist dystopian-utopian binaries and corporate imperatives to instead make space for collectively developing more diverse, creative, and multi-cultural AI imaginaries.

Practically, *Wilding AI* follows an approach to research-creation combining immersive sound creation, technical AI experimentation, and public engagement through residencies and open labs during media art festivals. This iterative approach integrates the public as a feedback mechanism during the research process (Bianchini 2015). The collective meets during festivals to experiment with custom AI tools, develop a common artistic language, and host public activities. Public activities have included an open studio at Hexagram Montreal in April 2024, two open labs at MUTEK Montreal 2024 and MUTEK Mexico 2024, a 4-day open call lab with a cohort of 13 artists at MONOM Studios during CTM Festival in Berlin in January 2025—discussed below—, and a public workshop at 4DSOUND during Amsterdam's Fiber Festival 2025. Between those activities, the collective works remotely toward developing the LLM behavior generator and preparing the production of an immersive audio creation to be premiered at the Society for Arts and Technology (SAT) in collaboration with MUTEK Montreal 2025.

The impulse to experiment with LLMs follows Jones's earlier artistic works *Soundscapes of an Earthly Community* (2023) and *feral.ai* (2024), which explored agentic sonic behaviors using YAMNET sound classification, IRCAM's RAVE audio model (Caillon and Esling 2021), and lightweight Ollama language models running on Raspberry Pi 5s. Through feedback loops with environments and audiences, those works explored the generation of sonic narratives by autonomous agents interacting with their surroundings.

To expand this art-technical exploration of LLMs toward automated expressive behavior, Jones sought the collaboration of Saunier. His research-creation practice engages with the problematic of machine agency through the development of artistic works—such as *SNN#2: Light-Space-Prop* (2019), which employs Spiking Neural Networks, and *Dynamiques Fluides* (2023), which combines Markov chains with musical improvisation—as well as hardware-software tools like the *MisbKit*, a modular robotic toolkit designed to prototype behavioral objects.

3 Sonic Agents and LLM Behavior Generator

3.1 Sonic Agent

Wilding AI takes the invitation of “imagining an AI that can be free” literally by experimenting with developing *sonic agents*. That is, AI-based agents whose sonic activity is generated

spontaneously in relation to their environment and expresses an internal, self-driven state from which intentions and psychological traits might be inferred (Levillain and Zibetti 2017; Penny 2017). Sonic agents relate to artificial life and living technologies (Langton 1995; Bedau et al. 2010), and immersive audio works involving, among others, self-organizing systems (Ikegami 2013), bio-inspired systems (Codognet and Pasquet 2010), and swarm behavior (Codognet and Pasquet 2010; Dziwis 2023).

The focus of sonic agents on the expression and sharing of agency across human and non-human actors (Ullrich and Trump 2023) contrasts with the application of agentic AI in musical production where musical agents are designed to automate creative tasks (Tatar and Pasquier 2019) such as composition (Blackwell and Young 2004; Eigenfeldt 2010) and improvisation (Lewis 2000; Banerji 2016). Recently, LLM-based agents have been developed for autonomous musical workflows (Yu et al. 2023) and symbolic music composition (Deng et al. 2024).

The use of LLMs in *Wilding AI* is thought of in the context of sonic agents possessing sensory, memory, narrative, decision-making, and expressive modules allowing them to listen to their environment, make autonomous decisions, and produce self-driven sonic behaviors. A first architecture of these envisioned agents was conceived by Saunier and Jones during a research-creation residency with Hexagram Montreal in April 2024. It stands as a constantly updating working hypothesis to guide development works and facilitate collective discussions (Figure 1). Due to practical constraints practical reasons, Saunier and Jones focused on the LLM behavior generator, leaving issues such as sensing for future developments.

3.2 Apparent Behavior

The LLM behavior generator serves as a composition technique to generate choreographies of sound (Baalman 2010), in which movements in space and modulations in time express the story, personality, and intention of the sonic agents—or, at least, enable spectators to project and attribute such inner states to them. In their study of *apparent behavior*, Heider and Simmel (1944) presented 114 participants with a short animation film in which two triangles and one circle move across the screen, entering and exiting a rectangular shape, colliding with each other, moving in synchrony, or crossing the screen at varying speeds. When asked to describe what they had seen, all but one participant recounted stories in which the shapes portrayed as characters—sometimes lovers, birds, or other figures—acting in a narrative story. Heider and Simmel observed that the qualities of motion performed by the triangle and circles as they move on the screen—in synchrony, opposition, pursuit, accelerations, or slowing down—enabled viewers to project stories, personalities, and intentions in otherwise lifeless geometrical shapes.

Extending the notion of apparent behavior into the fields of robotics and robotic art, Levillain and Zibetti define *behavioral objects* as entities that “produce specific cues that, to a human brain and to the naive psychology it generates, constitute meaningful indicators of an internal state and a disposition to interact with the world” (Levillain and Zibetti 2017). This practice of designing artworks that focus on the evocative projection arising from their temporal actions—particularly spatial motion—using computational processes that mimic cognitive functions gives rise to a new form of “aesthetics of behavior” (Penny 2000; 2017).

3.3 LLM-based Behavior

To experiment with expressive behaviors using LLMs, Saunier and Jones drew on the work of Yoshida, Matsumori, and Ikegami (2023) who developed an architecture to generate spontaneous action in the humanoid robot ALTER 3 using GPT-4. This architecture combines two cascading LLMs to produce a text-to-motion system that enables the humanoid to perform human-like behaviors out of prompts like “take a selfie” or “pretend to be a ghost.” This allows ALTER 3 to perform a wide range of bodily action and facial expressions without prior training, suggesting that LLMs such as GPT-4 contain an extensive representation of human behaviors. In further conversation experiments between ALTER 3 and human participants, ALTER 3 displayed facial expressions and bodily gestures relevant to the context of the discussion. By embodying GPT4 in real-world conversations through ALTER 3, they reflected that “the extensive language corpus of LLM, imbued with emotions and desires, presents untapped vitality.” While they noted this doesn't in itself demonstrate a true consciousness of

the kind that artificial intelligence and artificial life aims at, it nonetheless demonstrates the potential of LLMs to generate expressive behaviors suitable for artistic contexts.

Saunier and Jones employed a similar strategy to explore the potential of LLM language corpora to produce expressive sonic behaviors. This approach presented a challenge: while LLM training datasets include extensive literature on human motion readily adaptable to humanoid robots morphologically similar to the human body, the same may not hold true for abstract sonic motions and modulations.

The LLM behavior generator detailed below was developed iteratively in between the meetings of the *Wilding AI* collective. It was later integrated as a Max for Live device into Ableton Live by creative developer Noah Pred to provide an easy-to-use tool for the artists participating in the CTM Festival 2025 lab. Rather than a stable problem-solving piece of software, the LLM behavior generator aims to be an experimental boundary object (Star and Griesemer 1989) prone to support collaborative art-making and dialectical discussion between the members of the *Wilding AI* collective and with festival audiences.

Figure 1: Original diagram of the sonic agent drawn by Saunier and Jones during their Hexagram residency in April 2024. This initial sketch envisioned the use of sound analysis and classification to automatically prompt two cascading LLMs—augmented with memory modules—and generate movement in space, while the sound input was transformed using RAVE models.

4 Technical Implementation

4.1 General System

The LLM behavior generator was developed with Max/MSP, using node.js to query OpenAI's GPT API, and OSC to communicate with the 4DSOUND spatial audio software. Later work involved experiments with smaller local models including Meta's Llama 3.2, DeepSeek R1's, and Cohere for AI's Aya, the use of OSC communication to modulate sonic parameters in Ableton Live, and Pred's integration of Saunier's and Jones's work into an easy-to-use Max for Live device with added midi and transport functionalities.

The choice of the 4DSOUND software was motivated by the support of 4DSOUND and

MONOM Studios Berlin for the Wilding AI collective, which included access to their software and immersive audio environment—a 3D sound field composed of 48 omnidirectional loudspeakers arranged in a 4×4×3 cube, complemented by 9 subwoofers. Other systems such as SPAT will be used in future works.

4.2 LLM Behavior Generator

The LLM behavior generator produces dynamic sound spatialization and modulation in response to textual prompts (Figure 2). The current version of the LLM behavior generator requires artists to write textual prompts, or program their own automatic prompting systems. For example, an artist might prompt the agent to “jump in circles around the room” and hear the corresponding sound move in a circular motion, rising and falling dynamically, for about a minute. More complex and nuanced behaviors can be achieved as artists learn to write effective prompts for the system. In the future, input modules for automatic prompting will be developed using techniques such as sound categorization and movement analysis.

Figure 2: First iteration of the LLM behavior generator presented at Mutek Montréal 2024.

To the left, the original Max patch displays the prompt field in green, and the LLM-generated outputs in the gray fields below. Behind, Ableton Live was used to play audio tracks which were spatialized with the 4DSOUND software to the right.

To achieve this, the system uses a recipe-LLM and a code-LLM cascading into one another (Figure 3) following the architecture developed by Yoshida, Matsumori, and Ikegami (2023). Both LLMs use the same model—GPT-3.5 Instruct until September 2024, and then GPT-4o Mini—accessed via the OpenAI API. However, without memory of previous interactions, both LLMs operate fully independently.

When prompting the system, the recipe-LLM generates a sequence of steps describing the agent's motion in human language. Then, the code-LLM interprets the steps into numerical

data corresponding to spatialization and sonic parameters. Each step specifies a temporal duration in milliseconds, the X, Y, and Z destination coordinates of the sound, and additional float values corresponding to artist-defined sound modulation parameters mapped to controls within the DAW. Finally, a linear interpolation in Max/MSP smoothly ramps the position and parameter values from one step to the other before sending them over OSC to 4DSOUND and the DAW, respectively.

The LLM behavior generator operates on the hypothesis that LLMs can generate stories and describe actions when provided with specific situations—this is the role of the recipe LLM. It also assumes that LLMs can evaluate language—the role of the code LLM. Together, the recipe-LLM and code-LLM implement a Chain-of-Thought (CoT) process (Wei et al. 2023), in which the first LLM produces verbal descriptions and the second performs numerical evaluations of those descriptions. Once the behavior generator’s output is mapped onto the spatialization system and other sonic parameters, it is hypothesized that the resulting apparent behavior of the sound will be evocative enough for spectators to project stories, personalities, and intentions onto the sonic entity, much like the phenomenon demonstrated by Heider and Simmel.

Figure 3: Diagram of the architecture of the LLM behavior generator to produce spatial movement and sound modulations out of verbal prompts. The architecture was implemented in Max and node.js. Examples of task files and outputs correspond to experiments using GPT4. Architecture based on Yoshida et al. (2023).

4.3 Task Files

A prompt alone is not sufficient to produce the desired output from the recipe and code LLMs. In the background—and accessible to advanced users by modifying text files—a “recipe task file” is prepended to the user’s prompt before it is fed into the recipe-LLM. Similarly, a “code task file” is prepended to the recipe-LLM’s output before it is passed to the code-LLM. These

task files provide the guidelines that define how the LLMs should interpret the prompts and format their outputs.

The “recipe task file” is designed to obtain from the recipe-LLM a step-by-step sequence of actions corresponding to the agent's behavior in response to the artist's prompt. It functions like a bullet point narrative where each step indicates the agent's movement and the evolution of various “character traits,” internal qualities of the agent that lend themselves to generation and quantification by the LLM—i.e. happiness and curiosity. The task file first describes the agent's imagined personality, the space in which it evolves, and its character traits. Then, it specifies the expected output as a sequence of steps including the duration, destination position, and a brief description of each character trait.

The “code task file” instructs the code-LLM to translate the textual descriptions generated by the recipe-LLM into numerical values. For each “character trait” described by the recipe-LLM, the code-LLM provides a float between 0 and 1. For example, if the “recipe task file” asks for “a short description of the Joy of the agent limited to a maximum of four words,” the “code task file” asks the code-LLM to “imagine the numerical value that evaluates P1 as a float between 0 and 1,” given that “P1: A short description of the Joy of the agent limited to a maximum of four words.” Experiments to be developed further in later work suggest that the code-LLM’s ability to perform such numerical translation depends on the choice of “character trait,” which must lend itself to quantification.

4.4 Max for Live device

In order to integrate the use of the LLM behavior generator in sound making workflows adapted to non-expert users, a Max for Live device was developed by creative developer Noah Pred. It integrated the Max patch described previously within Ableton Live with additional features (Figure 4). Features included text fields to specify the sonic agent's “name” and “personality,” and drop-down menu to select character traits within a predefined list—indicated as “parameters” in the interface. Those fields automatically customize the task files. Other features include transport options—looping, quantization, sequence direction...—, MIDI mapping—values generated can be mapped to pitch, velocity, and duration—, and Ableton Live parameter mapping—values generated can be mapped to Ableton Live's interface objects. Finally, a “viewer” section displayed the generator's output in the form of lines, piano keyboard, and 2D space. A debug window logged the output of the LLMs. Additionally, an OSC input allowed to send prompts from the outside, bypassing the need to type, and an OSC output streamed the generated values.

The Max for Live device was used during the CTM Berlin 2025 lab and served as the basis for the performance described in the next section.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the Max for Live device used during the CTM Festival Berlin 2025 workshop. At the top, the two views of the device: the top one displays the MIDI control options, the bottom one the Live parameter mapping. From left to right, the interface allows for accessing task file parameters, prompting the LLMs, specifying Ableton Live transport parameters, specifying MIDI and/or parameter mapping, and visualizing the evolution of the output in the form of a graph, keyboard, and 2D space. At the bottom, two views of the debug window displaying the “recipe LLM” output (left) and “code LLM” output (right) resulting from the parameters and prompt in the device interface (top).

5 Performance case study

This section describes how Visi made use of the *Wilding AI* software during a 4-day lab at MONOM, a spatial sound studio and performance space in Berlin, Germany. The workshop took place in January 2025 as part of CTM Festival. The section is written in the first person from the perspective of Visi in order to make it more explicit that this is his own subjective

recount of the experience using the device.

I was introduced to the Wilding AI Max for Live device during a presentation on the use of LLMs and multi-agent systems in creative practice. The presentation included a short history of natural language processing (NLP) leading to LLMs, and an overview of some artistic works. As I am familiar with various AI concepts and techniques, I found the idea of chaining two LLMs with the purpose of translating minimal narratives written in natural language into sound trajectories appealing. Due to my research background, my interest was piqued by the perspective of using such an approach to probe the movements that are encoded into LLMs.

I first started experimenting with the Max for Live device in a casual manner, mapping the parameters generated by the device to Ableton stock synths and effects. This allowed me to get a sense of what the device could do before integrating it in more complex setups. My initial strategy was to map character traits such as “force”, “ferocity”, or “intensity” to sound parameters whose modulations are easy to recognise, such as distortion gain or filter cutoff frequency. Next I wrote prompts that described a character going through basic affective states, such as sadness, anger, and happiness. The results, to a certain extent, surprised me. What I found appealing was that the parameter modulations generally followed the narrative of my prompts in ways that made sense, yet often took unexpected turns that would be less likely if I had automated those parameters manually. Somehow it felt I could “disengage” from knobs and numerical values and play with higher-level, more abstract concepts to shape sounds in ways more akin to a brainstorming conversation.

Figure 5: Visi (left) and Gadi Sassoon (right), performing at MONOM studio, Berlin, 26 January 2025.

I explored the affordances of the device further in a duo performance with Gadi Sassoon using MONOM’s spatial sound system (Figure 5). The idea was to use six prompts to structure an improvisation between the two of us. These prompts formed a minimal narrative arc, which affected the parameters modulated by the LLM behavior generators, as well as our overall attitude during the improvisation. I played the Sophtar (Visi 2024), while Sassoon played a 5-string electric violin and live electronics. The LLM behavior generator determined the spatial

trajectories of the sound of my instrument inside MONOM, as well as three additional parameters: the amount of distortion applied to the sound of the strings, the volume of the output of a RAVE model (Caillon and Esling 2021), and the rate at which the Sophtar’s automated solenoids hit the strings.

Figure 6 shows the instance of the Wilding AI Max for Live device in my Ableton Live set. The name of the character used by the LLM behavior generator was “We” and its personality was “moody and confrontational.” The prompts used were:

1. *We start feeling the city's weight pressing down on us.*
2. *The tension permeates every aspect of our lives. We question how long we can endure.*
3. *We have a heated argument, prompting us to search for a way to break free from the cycle of frustration and despair.*
4. *A simple potluck dinner brings strangers together, sparking connections. We share a sense of shared understanding amid the chaos.*
5. *We grow into a community, collaborating on ideas like resource-sharing and local projects, fostering hope and resilience.*
6. *While the challenges persist, the solidarity of the community helps us feel stronger and more hopeful. We've finally found a way to push back against the city's weight.*

Figure 6: Wilding AI Max for Live device in Visi’s Ableton Live set, showing the settings for the character’s name, personality, traits, and final prompt.

The performance lasted approximately 12 minutes, I prompted the LLM behavior generator approximately every two minutes. The six prompts and the resulting behaviors generated by the LLMs worked as improvisation cues, enacting both some sonic modulations and an implicit narrative arc.

The trajectories generated by the system were never exactly the same, even when using the same prompts. However, I observed a certain consistency in the typical outputs of each prompt. Prompt #1 usually produced minimal movement and low values across the three additional parameters. These values gradually increased with prompts #2 and #3, the latter often showing the highest movement activity, with sound sources traveling across larger areas at higher speeds. Prompt #4, by contrast, generated slower trajectories with occasional short bursts of acceleration, while prompt #5 continued with even slower, smoother motion. Finally, prompt #6 brought another increase in speed, along with generally higher values across the three sound parameters.

6 Discussion

This paper captures the midpoint progress of the *Wilding AI* project after a first year of technical and creative experimentations involving LLMs and other generative AI tools. The following discussion arrives at an opportune moment to present preliminary observations and to reflect on the future direction of the project. The discussion draws from the authors’ experience with the LLM behavior generators and informal interactions with both members of

the collective and CTM workshop participants.

A recurring debate throughout all activities concerns the value of integrating LLMs in traditional music and sound design workflows. Does it make sense to integrate autonomous agents into DAWs to modulate sonic parameters, generate musical sequences, or automate spatialization? Among the challenges raised, prompting was often seen as a frustrating way to interact with sound. It required translating intuitive intentions into words in an effort that often failed to capture meaning in ways LLMs could interpret.

First, prompting introduced a material distance to the sonic material that was frustrating to musicians accustomed to play hands-on instruments. This led to suggestions for the development of automatic prompting features using sound and movement analysis.

Second, textual prompts similarly introduced a distance in the practice of composition. Musicians and sound artists frequently described their approach as an intuitive embodied process of playing and listening that bypassed verbal language. Many expressed that describing sounds and their behaviors in words felt not only unnatural, but, at times, outright impossible.

Third, language-based interactions with the LLMs challenged the artists not only to verbalize their intentions, but to do it in ways the sonic agents would interpret expressively. While very literal prompts like “draw a square” led to clear and predictable results, they felt uninteresting to most. On the other hand, prompts like “fly like a bird” produced seemingly random behaviors. Interestingly, enriching the prompts with qualifiers such as “a wounded bird” or “avoiding predators” would produce contrasting sonic dynamics that reflected the differences in the prompts.

Finally, the technical implementation of the LLM behavior generator—the mapping of its outputs and the definition of the task files—both enabled and constrained the expressivity of the sonic behavior. For instance, the mapping of the code LLM’s outputs onto sonic parameters constrained expressive dynamics to linear transitions. For example, prompts like “draw a circle” produced polygonal motions reminiscent of the circles of low definition computer graphics, and could be smoothed by instructing the LLM to produce more steps. Fundamentally, the task files’s instruction to produce step-based sequences necessarily enforced a form of temporally discrete behavior. The use of continuous interpolation—via Max’s line object—was a means to bring the LLMs’s output closer to the continuous domain of sound. Consequently, it was often unclear whether the expressive limitations attributed to the LLMs stemmed from them or from this specific Max/MSP implementation.

From Visi’s perspective, what is interesting about integrating such a tool in a performance and production environment involving DAWs and electronic musical instruments lies in the perspective of being able to relinquish agency and delegate some tasks to a system that is able to translate abstract concepts into sound parameters. In our view, this becomes an opportunity to add ways of developing sonic material performatively to established workflows centered on technique and explicit intention. To a certain extent, we see this as more akin to approaches such as Cage’s adoption of the I Ching or Eno and Schmidt’s *Oblique Strategies* than to a piece of software designed to accomplish a well-defined task as efficiently as possible. This aspect of the approach goes perhaps against narratives of labor reduction and currently associated with tools based on LLMs. This may create the expectation that LLMs tools like the *Wilding AI* device should be used to accomplish music production tasks more quickly and more easily. We resist this narrative and are more interested in tools that encourage exploration and co-creation.

Given that the prompts used in the performance were prepared in advance, one may wonder what the value of running the system live may be as opposed to storing and playing back trajectories generated previously. Interestingly, the trajectories generated by prompting the system with the same text were always different enough, and yet sufficiently consistent, to invite for improvisational exploration during the performance. Beyond introducing variability, live prompting the system also allows modify prompts during the performance and respond to the contingencies of the moment, creating space to change the course of the improvisation.

While the behaviors we observed in performance were interesting, it felt that gaining a deeper

understanding of what goes on under the hood, and developing more general prompting strategies, could—at least in Visi’s opinion—make the device more interesting in the longer term. This brings to mind Sturm’s research work on MIR systems (Sturm 2016): what is the “trick” behind our model? What actually causes its behavior?

7 Conclusion

This paper introduced the *Wilding AI* research-creation project which aims to explore artistic applications of generative AI to the media arts and, in particular, to immersive sound creation. The authors described an experimental LLM behavior generator developed by Saunier and Jones, presented a performance case study realised by Visi, and discussed insights on the application of LLMs to the creation of sonic behaviors.

In the case study described, working with natural language as an interface had the side effect of providing entry points into a narrative. This reverberated beyond the system itself, creating mood anchor points that aided the development of the performance. Performing with LLM systems enabled an embodied and enactive form of knowledge-making in line with the idea of the instrument as an epistemic tool (Magnusson 2009). Echoing the importance of play as a means of developing a personal understanding of opaque computing systems through trial and error (Turkle 2005), performing with such systems may help probe the kinds of behaviors encoded in the models and how they represent and relate different domains of knowledge.

Future works of the *Wilding AI* project will be the creation of immersive sound works to be premiered at the Society for Arts and Technology in collaboration with MUTEK Montréal 2025, experimentations with automated prompting using techniques such as sound and motion analysis, and further experiments with LLMs behavior generation focusing in particular on prompt engineering, retrieval augmented generation (RAG), and chain-of-thought architectures.

Furthermore, Saunier and Yoshida will develop hybrid qualitative-quantitative methodologies for analyzing the felt experience of LLM-driven behaviors expressed through sound and other media in the context of the research project “Performing Artificial Intelligence: Governance, Agency, Action—An Interdisciplinary Inquiry” funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation.

As a final reflection, we propose that the musical use of LLMs—and foundational models more broadly (Bommasani et al. 2022)—should be examined in light of the tradition of musical practices employing combinatorial, aleatoric, statistical, and other open-ended strategies in the exploration of new musical paradigms. These strategies—which may appear idiotic until they are not, as Beth Coleman (2021) reminds us—challenge normative frameworks and open us up to alternative sonic futures. That is, while mainstream uses of generative AI in sound often focus on applications like text-to-song or text-to-speech systems geared toward the reproduction of an aesthetic average and replacing artistic labor—often with problematic social, economical, intellectual, and cultural implications—the vitality of the artistic scenes embracing generative AI suggests alternative trajectories. If history has shown us anything, then the daring artists and researchers, who venture into these peripheral spaces—the wilder territories of artistic and technological experimentation—might well carve out a path for the emergence of novel creative paradigms.

As such, we find it productive to frame the musical, sonic and narrative use of LLMs through the historical lens of pioneering composers like John Cage’s use of indeterminacy, Iannis Xenakis’s stochastic processes, Brian Eno’s generative systems, George Lewis’s interactive systems, and the sonic fictions of Sun Ra. By granting autonomous systems compositional and performative agency, these practices develop what Simon Penny (Penny 2000) describes as an “aesthetic of behavior” that is “a new aesthetic field opened up by the possibility of cultural interaction with machine systems” that act autonomously, beyond human control. As technological agents increasingly take on problematics of cognition, sensory perception, and action that were once the sole purview of humans—such as musical composition and performance—, artists are faced with a new kind of artistic material that is not inert, but agential. This shift calls for new creative and relational paradigms where human-machine collaboration challenges traditional notions of authorship and control (Saunier and Howes 2023).

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